

PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT

Xasanova Taxmina

The student of Asia International University

Karimova Go'zal Ixtiyorovna

associated teacher, Asia International University.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13856858>

Abstract. Personal development is the same with the self-improvement consist of activities that develop a person's capabilities and potential, can increase human capability and enhance quality of life and facilitate the realization of dreams and aspirations. Personal development may take time to develop people's mind and their mental health. Because, they should strength their mental health by encountering various challenges in life and also it may take place over the course of an individual's entire lifespan and is not limited to one stage of a person's life.

Keywords: keywords of personal development- mental, emotional, physical, social and spiritual also it becomes clear that actual growth and fulfillment come from nurturing all aspects of self-being.

ЛИЧНОСТНОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ

Аннотация. Личностное развитие, как и самосовершенствование, состоит из действий, которые развивают способности и потенциал человека, могут повысить человеческие возможности и улучшить качество жизни, а также способствовать реализации мечтаний и стремлений. Личностное развитие может занять время, чтобы развить ум и психическое здоровье людей. Потому что они должны укреплять свое психическое здоровье, сталкиваясь с различными проблемами в жизни, и это может происходить на протяжении всей жизни человека и не ограничиваться одним этапом жизни человека.

Ключевые слова: ключевые слова личностного развития - умственное, эмоциональное, физическое, социальное и духовное, также становится ясно, что фактический рост и реализация происходят от возвращения всех аспектов самобытия.

Firstly, they should start improvement with ourselves. they should respect our feelings, thought and ourselves it can help them mentally. I feel that if they encountered with the bigger problem they try to solve it as soon as they can and also with this way that comes up with their mind they can broaden their critical thinking and self-improvements. they should read books one hour at least every day it can develop their brain function and also their point of view. Personal development also include self-esteem.

The following was written in answer to a 15-year-old girl's question, "How can they prepare themselves for a fulfilling life?"

They are them.

In all the world, there is no one else exactly like them. There are people who have some parts like them but no one adds up exactly like her. Therefore, everything that comes out of her is authentically mine because she alone choose it. she own everything about her – her body, including everything it does; her mind, including her thoughts and ideas; her eyes, including the images of all they behold; her feeling, whatever they might be- anger, joy, frustration, love, disappointment,

excitement; her mouth and all the words that come out of it – polite, sweet and rough , correct or incorrect; her voice, loud and soft; all her actions, whether her be to other or myself.

She own her fantasies, her dreams, her hobbies and her fears. She own all my triumphs and successes, all my failures and mistakes. Because She own all of her, She can become intimately acquainted with her. By so doing she can love herself and be friendly with her in all her parts. She can then make it possible for all of her to work in her best interests. She know there are aspects about herself that puzzle her, and other aspects that she do not know. But as long as she is friendly and loving to herself, she can courageously and hopefully look for the solutions to the puzzles and for ways to find out more about her. However I look and sound, whatever she say and do, and whatever she think and feel at a given moment in time is her.

This is authentic and represents where she am at that moment in time. When she review later how she looked and sounded, what she said and did, and how she thought and felt, some parts may turn out to be unfitting. She can discard that which is unfitting and keep that which proved fitting, and invent something new for that which she discarded. She can see, hear, feel, think, say and do. She have the tools to survive, to be close to others, to be productive, to make sense and order out of the world of people and things outside of her.

She own her and therefore she can engineer herself. She is her and she is okay.

Response/ Ability

The game they play is let's pretend and pretend they are not pretending they chose to forget who they are and then forget that they have forgotten who are we really? The center that watches and runs the show that can choose which way it will go. The she is consciousness that powerful loving perfect reflection of the cosmos but in our attempt to cope with early situations she chose or were hypnotized into a passive position to avoid punishment or the loss of love she chose to deny her response/ability pretending that things just happened or that she is being controlled taken over she put herself down and have become used to this masochistic posture this weakness this indecisiveness but she is in reality free a center of cosmic energy her will is her power don't pretend she don't have it or she won't .

Don't be afraid to fail for personal development

They have failed many times, although they may not remember. They fell down the first time you tried to walk. They almost drowned the first time they tried to swim, didn't you? Did you hit the ball the first time you swung a bat? Heavy hitters, the ones who hit the most home runs, also strike out a lot.

R.H. Macy failed seven times before his store in New york caught on. English novelist John Creasey got 753 rejection slips before he published 564 books. Babe Ruth struck out 1,330 times, but he also hit 714 home runs. Don't worry about failure. Worry about the chances he miss when he don't even try.

For them to be more creative, they are waiting for... Power of Determination

Inspiration, permission, reassurance, their turn, someone to smooth the way, the rest of rules, someone to change, wider fairways, revenge, the stakes to be lower, more time, a significant relationship to improve, terminate, happen, the right person, a disaster, annual checkup, a better circle of friends, logic to prevail.

Conclusion: Personal development and self-care are essential for career growth and success. Invest in yourself by setting goals, learning new skills, seeking feedback, practicing self-care, and networking. Also they should build their notions.

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